

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

PROJECT ACTIVITY AS A CONNECTION BETWEEN THEORY AND PRACTICE

Davletova A.,

*Master's student of the philological faculty,
West Kazakhstan University named after M. Utemisov*

Kismetova G.

*Scientific Supervisor
Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
West Kazakhstan University named after M. Utemisov*

Abstract

Nowadays, there is a gradual process of reorientation of the education system from knowledge to a predominantly competence-based model, which assumes not only the availability of the necessary knowledge, but also the ability to use it. The most important pedagogical task is the formation of students' skills to navigate the expanding information space, to extract and apply knowledge, to use the acquired knowledge to solve cognitive and practical exercises. The introduction of methods and technologies of project activity into the educational process should help students acquire the above-listed skills. In this article, it is assumed that by performing project work, students will become more proactive and responsible, increase the effectiveness of educational activities, gain additional motivation, learn how to apply the knowledge they have gained in new situations.

Keywords: project activity, project methods, students, practice.

Currently, Kazakhstan is developing its own plan and national model of Education. In this regard, one of the educational technologies aimed at the personal development of students is project activity. Today, project activity is the most common type of intellectual activity used in various fields. In the modern understanding, a project is a prototype of some type of activity or object. It allows teachers to evaluate not only the preparatory process, but also the final result of the student's activities. As noted by the Doctor of Law, Professor, Head of the Department of International Law A.A. Sabitova, that "The main function of most research and educational institutions is the implementation of scientific research in the field of education, training, dissemination of research results. Therefore, project activity provides a connection between theory and practice, and an educational project is a joint educational and cognitive, creative activity with a common goal, coordinated approaches to activity aimed at achieving a certain result.[1]. It is both a task for students formulated in the form of a problem, and their purposeful activity, and a form of organization of interaction between students and a teacher and students among themselves, and the result of activity as a way they found to solve the problem of the project[2]. The task of the project method is the development of cognitive, creative skills of students, the ability to independently construct their knowledge, the ability to navigate in the information space, the development of critical thinking. In the curriculum of education of the Republic of Kazakhstan there is a section called "Project activity". Therefore, every student is familiar with this type of activity. The very word "project" sets students up for serious, meaningful work and teaches them independence[3]. Thus, the project activity allows students to go beyond the volume of college or university subjects, make interdisciplinary connections, combine existing life experience with new knowledge, develop an active life position, and maximize creative opportunities.

Project work preparation of a college or university student is one of the most necessary elements of the education system of Kazakhstan. This is preparation for the formation of the student's own research abilities, (including consideration of the issue, a set of information and the work develops the ability to communicate and logical thinking. Usage of project activity is aimed at improving the quality of education in the Republic of Kazakhstan [4].

The involvement of students in the project method of teaching is purely scientific or not only for the purpose of acquiring knowledge, but also professional knowledge processes that organize and determine the student's interest as a result, the In this turn, the method of project learning performs two cognitive functions at the same time: on the one hand, it is learning the method of deepening the acquired knowledge and abilities on the other hand practical application for the certain purpose [5]. As a rule, most often, the final result of the project activity is the participation of students in scientific and practical conferences and competitions. Among the advantages of this technology is the provision of an opportunity for an average child to reveal his unrealized potential at practically any stage of educational activity at school and when studying almost any part of the academic discipline. At the same time, a participant in such an intellectual competition acquires the skills of certain communicative skills, develops perseverance, learns self-control that much needed qualities to implement and present his research in a contest or conference [6].

The most important part of the planning project work in colleges or universities is the step-by-step development of the project, which provides a list of specific actions with the results, deadlines and those responsible. The research work of students is a prerequisite for each project. There is no single point of view that the project should be individual or group. Some

teachers allow only individual projects, others believe that only group projects are effective.

Advantages of individual projects: - the work plan for the project can be drawn up and controlled with maximum accuracy. - the student develops a sense of responsibility, because the implementation of the project depends only on him; the student receives experience at all stages of the implementation of the project: from thought to final reflection. - the student develops important skills: research, presentation, evaluation. Advantages of group projects. - communication skills are formed; - each student has the opportunity to appear as a leader at a certain stage. - the ability to consider many ideas, hypotheses, points of view and various ways to solve the problem; - the element of competition increases the motivation of participants and has a positive effect on the quality of project execution[7]. Students' project activity is subject to a certain algorithm and is complex, consisting of several stages of creative, research work. This is how the project methodology differs from working on a topic, in which it is often quite easy to learn new material on the topic; from role-playing, discussion, etc., in which roles are distributed in group work to implement the following methodological plan: better assimilation material, stimulating interest, motivating cognitive activity of students. All these methodological goals may be present when using the project methodology, but, among other things, it is necessarily inherent in the study of the problem, creative search activity embodied in any particular product. [8]

However, the work on the project may contain certain difficulties. Students are not always ready or able to carry out project activities in foreign language: to conduct a discussion, discuss organizational issues, present the progress. Language errors are also inevitable, since some of the additional information is unfamiliar to students and causes certain language difficulties. Therefore, the repetition and generalization of the necessary grammatical and lexical material should precede the development of projects, and it is advisable to carry out the projects themselves at the final stage of work on the topic, when conditions have already been created for free improvisation in working with language and speech material. Completing project tasks and participating in the project allows students to see the practical benefits of studying foreign language, as a result of which it is aimed at increasing interest in the academic subject, research work in the process of "acquiring knowledge" and their conscious application in various foreign language speech situations, which means it contributes to the increase of students' communicative competence, the development of their linguistic personality, high motivation of students. The effectiveness of project work depends on many factors that must be monitored by the teacher when planning a project. Knowledge of the main features of the typology of the project is a prerequisite for the successful implementation of the project, which means the implementation of productive foreign language speech activity of students in the learning process[9].

Experimental

Methods: content analysis, the inductive-deductive method

The experimental work on implementing project work was conducted at pedagogical college in Uralsk with 2nd year students. After the discussion with students we came to an agreement on a project theme « Idioms». Their main task was to identify the most effective methods of learning idioms. We worked out project details that guided students from the opening activity to the completion of the project. The students considered their roles, and collaborative work groups. They worked together and assigned the roles and responsibilities. They reached a consensus on the timing for gathering, sharing, and compiling information, and then presenting their final project. As important criterion for the success of this project work was the creation of the necessary conditions, students were provided with a list of credible resources and explained where they can find information. As the quality of training directly depended on the techniques and methods used, methods of SWOT and SMART analysis, health-saving technologies and brainstorming techniques were used during the implementation of project work. In addition, several online tools such as Edpuzzle (was used for creating videos about Idioms), PlanbookEdu (free online teaching tool that let students to plan their project work) and Flipgrid (online service that provided a simple, free, and accessible video discussion experience for learners to discuss the topic of project work and share the information) were also applied during the process. Moreover, students were given rubric on how their work will be graded and hints on how students can improve their projects and what they can add to it throughout the course.

The final Canva presentation of the group lasted within a period (30 minutes). The performance was given in the students' classroom in front of the teachers and other groups. The evaluation finalized the project. The students looked back at the activities they followed. They also made comments on their efforts as well as got constructive feedbacks from the other group members and groupmates in doing the project. During the process of the project all students showed active participation. It is worth mentioning that while working for preparing their presentation the students worked closely together, thus establishing good relations with each other. contribute and motivated to do well. The teacher played the role of the guide and facilitator encouraging students to work together, to communicate in English and present their work step by step in the class.

Project activity taught our students to apply the essential knowledge and skills learned in the classroom and stimulated the independent cognitive activity of students. In addition, it blurred the boundaries between college disciplines, thereby bringing the learning process closer to real life.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, project based method is a way to apply acquired knowledge through a complete processing of the problem, which must be completed in some way with a well – designed, concrete, significant practical result. In the pedagogical process using project training – educational services, teaching methods and techniques, forms and technical means of training are considered in connection with the basics of project methods. Thus, one of the main tasks of a modern teacher is to create a favorable environment in the classroom and extracurricular activities, in which students will be able to fully realize their educational and creative potential. Students should feel their importance, independence, otherwise it can lead to a loss of interest in project activities, especially if the student has a high level of creative thinking and has the qualities of a leader. When organizing activities, it is necessary to take into account individual characteristics student. The teacher should be able to organize the work correctly at each of its stages, maintaining the interest and motivation of students, unobtrusively monitor and direct activities in the right direction.

References

1. 2020. Musa K.A. Project-based learning as the basis of the education system
2. Sabitova A.A. International and legal aspect of interstate cooperation in the field of education. // Bulletin of KazNPU. Series International Life and Politics. – 2016. – № 4 (47). Pp. 20-21
3. 2017. Gubernskaya S.I. "Project activity as a means of developing cognitive activity and professional competence of students"
4. 2014. Madieva G.B., Utepova G.N., Iskakova G.N. Methodical instructions for the implementation of the project work. Almaty: Kazakh university
5. 2022. N. B. Kiyakbay1, N. Z. Zhumanbekova. Language skills through a training project language personality development. L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Republic of Kazakhstan, Nur-Sultan
6. 2018. P.A. Kissabekova, A.Zh. Zhakupova, M. Serik, A.A. Bogdanova Project technology as a means of forming key competencies in the educational process
7. 2020. Nupirova A.M. The project method as a tool for the formation of functional literacy of students Kostanay State Pedagogical University named after U. Sultangazin, Kostanay.
8. 2020. Poleyaya N. M., Sitnikova V. V. Fundamentals of project activities
9. 2022. Poobalan, G., Asman, J., Talip, R., Padan, R., Kaliappan, S., Micheal, C., & Marcus, L. Creative Project Work as A 21st-Century Education Tool. International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development, 11(3), 167–176.